

SHORT NOTES

Zinc Content of Some Marine Bivalves and Barnacles from Bombay Shores

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Zinc has been reported to be occurring in tissues of marine invertebrates from different parts of the world¹. The zinc content of some species of these invertebrates is so high as to permit their use as 'indicator organisms' for detection of the long-lived activation product Zn-65 in seawater. This was further corroborated by the significant concentrations of Zn-65 in the coastal organisms of California, found by Folsom *et al.*², and by the accumulation of radioactive zinc in marine shell-fish, observed by Chipman *et al.*³ It has therefore been considered of interest to determine the extent to which zinc is accumulated by different species of marine invertebrates from Bombay shores.

The freshly collected samples were washed free of extraneous matter after removal of the shells and the soft-parts were dried in a hot-air oven at 100°. Zinc was estimated by the dithizone mixed colorimetric method, described by Sandell⁴. The results of analyses are recorded in Table I in parts per million parts of wet weight.

TABLE I

Species.	No of samples analysed.	Average Zn content (p. p. m.).	Range (p. p. m.).
<i>Kateleyxia marmorata</i>	10	11.0	5.9 — 18.0
<i>Meretrix meretrix</i>	4	14.8	12.0 — 15.9
<i>Mytilus viridis</i>	1	11.0	11.0
<i>Crassostrea cucullata</i>	2	254.5	129.4 — 379.6
<i>Crassostrea madrasensis</i>	2	203.4	171.0 — 236.5
<i>Balanus amphitrite communis</i>	4	71.5	40.2 — 92.3

Zinc was also determined in 12 seawater samples from Bombay coast and the average content was found to be 28 µg./litre.

The results indicate that the concentration of zinc is highest in the oysters and that the rock-oyster, *C. cucullata*, and the backwater oyster, *C. madrasensis*, accumulate zinc from seawater by factors of the order of 10000. The average zinc content of the barnacle, *B. amphitrite communis*, falls between that of oysters and clams. In the clams (*K.*

- (1) A.P. Vinogradov, "The Elementary Chemical Composition of Marine Organisms". New Haven; Sears Foundation for Marine Research, Yale University, 1953.
- (2) *Nature*, 1963, 200, 200, 327.
- (3) *Fishery Bull.*, No. 135, Vol. 58, 1958, Washington: U.S. Dept. of Fish and Wildlife Service.
- (4) "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals" 3rd ed., Interscience Publishers, New York.

marmorata and *M. meretrix*) the zinc content ranges from 5.9 to 18.0 p.p.m., whereas the mussel, *M. viridis*, contains 11.0 p.p.m. of zinc.

In regard to mussels, it would be interesting to extend the studies to a large number of observations on the species of *Mytilus* available in India and to compare the data with those obtained on mussels elsewhere. This assumes special significance in view of the active search that is going on for 'indicator' species with a worldwide distribution.

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